

Effect of boiling and baking times on the functional properties of aerial yam (*Dioscorea bulbifera*) flours cv *Dugu-won* harvested in Côte d'Ivoire

Jacques Y. Achy, Gbocho Serge Elvis Ekissi*, Pamphile Kouadio Bony Koffi, Fankroma Martial Thierry Koné, Lucien Patrice Kouamé

Department of Food Science and Technology, University Nangui Abrogoua (ex University Abobo, Adjame), Laboratory of Biocatalysis and Bioprocessing, Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire

Article published on February 28, 2017

Key words: Baking, Boiling, Flours, *Dioscorea bulbifera*, Functional properties

Abstract

The study examined the effect of boiling and baking times on the functional properties of aerial yam (*Dioscorea bulbifera*) flours in order to assess which one can ameliorate better their functional properties. Boiling and baking times affected significantly ($P < 0.05$) the functional properties of *D. bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* flours. They increased the water absorption capacity (WAC), water solubility index (WSI), bulk density (BD) dispersibility (D), least gelation concentration (LGC), paste clarity (PC), swelling power (SP) and solubility of aerial yam flours cv *Dugu-won*. But they decreased iodine affinity of starch, foam capacity and foam stability. The boiling increased the absorption capacity of olive oil, maize oil, red oil, dinor oil and sunflower oil from *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours. The baking decreased the absorption capacity of the same oils. Boiling and baking have been found to give good functional properties which can be of high importance in food manufacturing industries. However boiling ameliorated better functional properties of aerial yam flours cv *Dugu-won* than baking.

*Corresponding Author: Gbocho Serge Elvis Ekissi ✉ ekiss_esg@yahoo.com

Introduction

Yams, the edible tubers of various species of the genus *Dioscorea*, are important staple foods and a potential source of ingredients for fabricated foods in many tropical countries because of their high starch content (Survey, 2012). It is a major staple food for an estimated 60 million people in the region stretching from Côte d'Ivoire to Cameroon, an area commonly referred to as "Yam Zone" of West Africa (Akissoe *et al.*, 2003; Jimoh and Olatidoye, 2009). They are the most preferred of all roots and tubers by millions of people in the yam zones of Africa (FAO, 1985).

Yams are cultivated mainly in three areas of the world: West-Africa and parts of East, Central and Southern Africa (FAO, 1999) are the primary cultivation areas, producing about 95 % of the world yam production followed by Southeast Asia including China, Japan and Oceania. Only a few species of yams are cultivated as food crops. Yams are an excellent source of starch, which provides caloric energy (Coursey, 1973). Yams are widely grown and consumed amongst various communities in the tropics, amongst them is the *Dioscorea bulbifera* also known as potato yam or air potatoes. It is an aerial yam which is cultivated in the Southeast Asia, West Africa, South and Central America.

Dioscorea bulbifera is available in two varieties, the edible and non-edible. The edible varieties are cultivated and widely distributed in West Africa, West Indies, South Pacific, and South East Asia (FAO, 1985; Survey, 2012). *Dioscorea bulbifera* is among the most important tuber crops in West Africa. It is included in the roots and tubers which are widely distributed throughout the tropics with only a few in the temperate regions of the world (Coursey, 1967; FAO, 1996). Together with cereals they constitute the main source of energy in the tropics. This yam species produced aerial starchy bulbils. Bulbils weighing up one kilogram are not exceptional but those of 200-300 g are usual (Degras, 1986).

In Côte d'Ivoire, two cultivars of *D. bulbifera* are used for plantation. The first one is a cultivar with a greater size bulbils and a yellow flesh.

Its local name is *Dugu-won*. The second named *Won-kpia* has small bulbils with mauve colored flesh (Libra *et al.*, 2011).

In Bété's country (forest population in western Côte d'Ivoire), *Dioscorea bulbifera* is cultivated for their bulbils which are consumed once cooked like potatoes in water with oil and local ingredients. *Dioscorea bulbifera* is a good source of iron, phosphorus and calcium (Tandall, 1983; Abara *et al.*, 2000, Achy *et al.*, 2016). Before eating, the yam *Dioscorea bulbifera* must be cooked. Several cooking processes are used for it. There are boiling, steaming, baking and grilling on embers. Cooking has been reported to either be beneficial or detrimental to the nutritional content of food (Chukwu *et al.*, 2010).

But we don't know if cooking ameliorated functional properties of yam *Dioscorea bulbifera*. Most of the yams are consumed after being cooked or processed. In general, yams are prepared at home on the basis of convenience and taste preference rather than retention of nutrient and health-promoting compounds (Masrizal *et al.*, 1997). Moreover, yams are always cooked before being eaten. Yams nutrients and functional properties appear to be influenced by cooking methods. However, there is no consistent information on the effects of thermal treatments on the properties of its constituents.

The objective of this study was to assess the effect of cooking (baking and boiling) times on functional properties of bulbil flours (*Dioscorea bulbifera*) in order to choose the best cooking process which can ameliorate the functional properties.

Materials and methods

Materials

Bulbils (aerial yam) of *Dioscorea bulbifera* (cultivar *Dugu-won*) used for this work were randomly harvested at maturity (6 months after planting) from a farm in Agou, South-East portion of Côte d'Ivoire (West Africa). They were immediately transported to Laboratory and stored under prevailing tropical ambient conditions (19-28°C, 60-85%) for 24 hours before the preparation of flours from raw and boiled and baked bulbils of *Dioscorea bulbifera* (cv *Dugu-won*).

Flours Processing

Bulbils (5kg) were washed with clean tap water, peeled and sliced into cubes then rinsed with distilled and deionized water. The slices were divided into seven parts of 500g each. Three parts of the sliced were boiled at 100°C for 10 (FE10), 20 (FE20) and (FE30) minutes. Three parts of the sliced were baked at 100°C for 10 (FF10), 20 (FF20) and (FF30) minutes. The remaining one part (FNT0) and the cooked six parts were put into an oven and dried at 45°C for 2 days. The dried samples were ground into fine powder to pass through a 250 µm sieve. Dried powder samples were packed into airtight sealed plastic bags and stored in the refrigerator for later analysis.

Functional properties evaluation

Iodine affinity of starch (IAS)

The iodine affinity of starch of flours from bulbils (*Dioscorea bulbifera*, cv *Dugu-won*) was assayed using guidelines of Kawabata *et al.* (1984). Three (3) g of flour were introduced into 50 ml beakers and made up to 30 ml dispersions using distilled water. The dispersion was stirred occasionally within the first 30 min and then filtered through Whatman no.42 filter paper. A 10 ml aliquot of the filtrate was pipetted into a conical flask, phenolphthalein was added and the filtrate titrated with 0.1N I₂ solution to a bluish back end-point. The starch cell damage (free starch content) was calculated using the titre value and expressed as iodine affinity of starch. IAS (ppm):

$$\text{IAS (ppm)} = \frac{VD \times Vt \times Na}{VA \times Ms \times 100} \times 10^6$$

Where VD = Total volume of dispersion; VA = Volume of aliquot used titration,
Vt = Titre value, Ms = Mass (db) of flour used, Na = Normality of iodine solution used

Flour dispersibility (D)

The flour dispersibility was determined by the method described by Kulkani *et al.*, (1991). 10g of flour were weighed into 100ml measuring cylinder and distilled water added to make a volume of 100ml. The set up was stirred vigorously for 1min. The volume of the settled particles was registered after regular time step of 30min.

The volume of settled particles was subtracted from 100. The difference was reported as percentage of dispensability.

Paste clarity (PC)

The paste clarity was determined according to the method of Craig *et al.* (1989). A 1% aqueous suspension was made by suspending 0.2g of flour in 20ml of distilled water in a stoppered centrifuge tube and vortex mixed. The suspension was heated in a boiling water (100°C) bath for 30min. After cooling, clarity of the flour was determined by measuring percent transmittance at 650nm against water blank on a spectrophotometer JASCO V-530 (UV/VIS, Model TUDC 12 B4, Japan Servo CO, LTD Indonesia).

Least Gelation Concentration (LGC)

Appropriate sample suspension of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16 and 20% w/v were prepared in 5 ml distilled water. The test tubes containing these suspensions were heated for 1 hour. The tubes are quickly cooled at 4°C. The least gelation concentration was determined as concentration when the sample from the inverted test tube did not fall down the slip (Coffman and Garcia, 1977).

Bulk density (BD)

The method described by Oladele and Ainaby (2007) was used for the determination of bulk density. 50 g of *D. bulbifera* bulbils flour was put into 100 ml measuring cylinder. The measuring cylinder was then tapped continuously on a laboratory table until a constant volume was obtained. BD (g/cm³) was calculated using following the formula:

$$\text{BD (g/cm}^3\text{)} = \frac{\text{Weight of sample}}{\text{Volume of sample after tapping}}$$

Water absorption capacity (WAC) and Water solubility index (WSI)

The water absorption capacity and solubility index of flours from bulbils of *Dioscorea bulbifera*, cv *Dugu-won* were evaluated according to Phillips *et al.* (1988) and Anderson *et al.* (1969) methods respectively. 1g of flour samples (M₀) was each weighed into a centrifuge tube and 10ml distilled water added. The content of the centrifuge tube was shaken for 30min in a KS 10 agitator.

The mixture was kept in a water bath (MEMMERT) (37°C) for 30min and centrifuged (ALDRESA, DITACEN II) at 5000rpm for 15min.

The resulting sediment (M_2) was weighed and then dried at 105°C to constant weight (M_1). The WAC and WSI were then calculated as follows:

$$\text{WAC (\%)} = \frac{M_2 - M_1}{M_1} \times 100$$

$$\text{WSI (\%)} = \frac{M_2 - M_1}{M_1} \times 100$$

Oil absorption capacity (OAC)

The oil capacity of flours from *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils was evaluated according to Eke and Akobundu (1993) methods. 1 g of sample (M_0) was mixed with 10ml in a weighed 20ml centrifuge tube. The slurry was agitated on a vortex mixer for 2min, allowed to stand at 28°C for 30min and then centrifuged at 4500rpm for 30min. The clear supernatant was decanted and discarded. The adhering drops of oil were removed and the tube was weighted (M_1). The AOC was calculated as follows:

$$\text{OAC (\%)} = \frac{M_0 - M_1}{M_0} \times 100$$

Foam capacity (FC) and foam stability (FS)

The foam capacity (FC) and stability (FS) of flour from *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils were studied by the method of Coffman and Garcia (1977). 3g of flour was transferred into clean, dry and graduated (50 ml) cylinders. The flour samples were gently level and the volumes noted. Distilled water (30 ml) was added to each sample; the cylinder was swirled and allowed to stand for 120 min while the change in volume was recorded every 10 min. The FC (%) and FS (%) values were calculated as follows:

$$\text{FC (\%)} = \frac{V_t - V_o}{V_o} \times 100$$

$$\text{FS (\%)} = \frac{\text{FC}}{\text{FC}_0} \times 100$$

Where V_o (ml) is the original volume of sample, V_t is the total volume after different times (ml) and FC_0 is the foam capacity at 0 min.

Swelling Power (SP) and Solubility

The effect of temperature on swelling and solubility was carried out according to the method of Adebooye and Singh (2008). 0.5g of the flour sample (W) was accurately weighed and quantitatively transferred into a clean dried test tube and weighed (W_1). The flour was then dispersed in 50cm³ of distilled water using stirrer. The slurry obtained was heated for 30min at various temperatures from 50°C to 100°C. The mixture was cooled at room temperature and centrifuged for 15min at 2600rpm. The residue obtained after centrifugation with the water was retained and the test tube was weighed (W_2). Aliquots (5ml) of the supernatant were dried to a constant weight at 110°C. The residue obtained after drying solubilized in water. Solubility was calculated as g per 100g of starch on dry weight basic. Swelling power was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{SP (g/g)} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W}$$

Statistical analysis

All analyses were carried out in triplicates. Statistical significance was established using one-way analysis of Variance (ANOVA) models to estimate the effect of treatment on functional properties of flours from aerial yam (*D.bulbifera*) at 5% level. Means were separated according Tukey's (HSD) test at $P < 0.05$, with the help of the software.

Results and discussion

Functional properties of food are defined as physicochemical properties reflecting complex interactions between the composition, structure, conformation and physicochemical properties components (Kohnhorst *et al.*, 1990). The aerial yam flours functional properties could be influenced by cooking times. There could have significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between raw and cooked breadfruit pulp flours functional properties.

The water absorption capacity (WAC) is presented in Table 1. The WAC is the ability to absorb or retain water. It is a functional property used in determining the suitability of utilising a material in baked foods such as bread where high WAC is needed (Onuegbu *et al.*, 2001).

The boiling water and baking from *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) WAC after 30min. Similar results were reported by Koné *et al.* (2014) who showed increasing WAC values in flours from yam *kponan* (*D. cayenesi-rotundata*). The WAC from *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours range between 175 ± 5.20 to $236 \pm 3.46\%$ for boiling water after 30min. The WAC from *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours range between 150 ± 3.46 to $167 \pm 2\%$ for baking after 30 min. The WAC for the boiling water and baking in ours study were lower than those obtained for cooked breadnut flours (290-310%) (Nwabueze *et al.*, 2008) and pre-cooked cocoyam (247.5-562.5%) (Fagbemi *et al.*, 2006). The ability of food to absorb water may be sometimes attributed to its proteins content (Kinsella, 1976). The denatured proteins in flours due to heat processing bind more water and hence could lead to flour higher water absorption (Otis and Akobundu, 2007).

According to Aryee (Aryee *et al.*, 2006), water absorption capacity depends on the associative forces among starch components where weak inter associative forces result into high water binding capacity. Water absorption capacity is the ability of flour particles to entrap large amounts of water, such that exudation is prevented (Chen and Lin, 2002).

The water solubility index (WSI) reflects the extent of starch degradation (Diosady *et al.*, 1985). The WSI ($17.31 \pm 0.80\%$) observed for the flour of raw *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils is lower compared to that of flour from boiled (20.25 ± 1.98 to $36.85 \pm 2.66\%$) and baking (18.20 ± 0.17 to $26 \pm 1.73\%$) *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils (Table 1), indicating that boiling and baking have more profound effect on starch degradation. Similar observations were recorded by Hsu *et al.* (2003), when using yam *Dioscorea* spp flours (9.26 ± 0.11 to $15.31 \pm 0.85\%$).

Table 1. Functional properties of aerial yam (*Dioscorea bulbifera*) flours cv *Dugu-won* during boiling and baking times.

	Functional properties (%)							
	WAC	WSI	FC	D	BD (g/cm ³)	IAS (ppm)	PC	LGC
	Aerial yam Flours and boiling times							
FNT0	149.42 ± 4.50^A	17.31 ± 0.80^A	26.67 ± 0.26^I	16 ± 1.73^A	0.72 ± 0.02^A	53 ± 4.36^J	43 ± 1.73^A	2
FE10	175 ± 5.20^C	20.25 ± 1.98^{AB}	20.88 ± 1.06^{FG}	25 ± 1.73^{BC}	0.74 ± 0.02^{AB}	45 ± 4.58^{GHI}	46 ± 2.65^{ABC}	4
FE20	197 ± 3.46^A	27.10 ± 2.76^{DE}	15.82 ± 0.39^{CD}	29 ± 1.15^{CDE}	0.76 ± 0.01^{AB}	36 ± 3.46^{CDE}	62 ± 2.65^E	8
FE30	236 ± 3.46^F	36.85 ± 2.66^G	13 ± 1.73^{BC}	36 ± 1^{GH}	0.82 ± 0.02^{CD}	27 ± 2.65^{BC}	66 ± 2^F	14
	Aerial yam Flours and baking times							
FNT0	149.42 ± 4.50^A	17.31 ± 0.80^A	26.67 ± 0.26^I	16 ± 1.73^A	0.72 ± 0.02^A	53 ± 4.36^J	43 ± 1.73^A	2
FF10	150 ± 3.46^A	18.20 ± 0.17^{AB}	25.12 ± 2.34^{HI}	18 ± 2.65^A	0.73 ± 0.03^A	50 ± 5.20^{IJ}	44 ± 2.65^{AB}	4
FF20	160 ± 4.36^B	22 ± 1.73^{BC}	23.70 ± 2.34^{GH}	24 ± 2.65^{BCD}	0.74 ± 0.03^{AB}	44 ± 5.20^{FGHI}	46 ± 1.73^{ABC}	6
FF30	167 ± 2^B	26 ± 1.73^{DE}	21.16 ± 1.04^{FG}	30 ± 2.65^{EFG}	0.76 ± 0.03^{AB}	40 ± 3.46^{EFG}	49 ± 1.73^{CD}	8

Values are means of triplicate determination Means with different superscript in the same column are significantly different from each other at ($P > 0.05$) WAC=Water Absorption Capacity; WSI=Water Solubility Index; FC= Foam Capacity; D= Flour Dispersibility; BD= Bulk Density; IAS=Iodine Affinity of Starch; PC=Paste Clarity; LGC=Least Gelation Concentration

The dispersibility is an useful functional parameter which give information to flours ability to reconstitute in water to have a fine and consistence paste and give an indication of good water-absorption capacity (Kulkarni *et al.*, 1991). In our work, the result in Table 1 showed that boiling and baking increased bulbils flours after 30 min. Their values ranged respectively from $25 \pm 1.73\%$ to $36 \pm 1\%$ and $18 \pm 2.65\%$ to $30 \pm 2.65\%$. These results were lower than those reported by Eke-Ejiofor *et al.* (2011) who reported the respective values 55-66% and 50-70% for local rice of Nigeria and Caprice rice.

The increasing dispersibility of flour from *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils could may be caused by starch gelatinisation which increases the water-binding capacities (Dengate, 1984).

The bulk density (BD) of bulbils flours are presented into Table 1. The result showed that BD of bulbils decreased in boiling and baking after 30min. They values ranged respectively from $0.74 \pm 0.02 \text{g/cm}^3$ to $0.82 \pm 0.02 \text{g/cm}^3$ and $0.73 \pm 0.03 \text{g/cm}^3$ to $0.76 \pm 0.0 \text{g/cm}^3$.

The raw flour of *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils (0.72 ± 0.02 g/cm³) is similar to that from wheat flours (0.71 g/cm³) (Akubor, 2007) but low than those of raw and fermented wheat flours with respective value 0.80 and 0.86 g/cm³ (Ijarotomi, 2007). BD gives an indication of the relative volume of packaging material required. Generally, higher BD is desirable for greater ease of dispersibility and reduction of paste thickness (Padmashree *et al.*, 1987; Udensi and Eke, 2000). Low BD of flours are good physical attributes when determining transportation and storability since the products could be easily transported and distributed to required locations (Agunbiade and Sanni, 2003). Low BD is advantageous for the infants as both calorie and nutrients density in enhanced per feed of the child (Onimawo and Egbekun, 1998). High bulk density is a good physical attribute when determining mixing quality of particulate matter (Lewis, 1990).

The iodine affinity of starch from raw bulbils *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* flour (53 ± 4.36 ppm) is lower than those for flour from boiled bulbils (27 ± 2.36 ppm to 45 ± 4.58 ppm and baked bulbils (40 ± 3.46 ppm to 50 ± 5.20 ppm). The result (Table 3) showed that the boiled and baked bulbils flours contained starch granules with the high affinity for iodine or in consonance with reports by Raja (1992) contains more amylose. Brunnschweiler *et al.* (2006) reported that amylose aggregation has a strong impact on the texture of the pastes.

The paste clarity (PC) is an important that governs different applications of flours and starches for food processing. Light transmittance of *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours obtained by boiling and baking (Table 1) ranged respectively from 43 ± 1.73 to $66 \pm 2\%$ and 43 ± 1.73 to $49 \pm 1.73\%$. The low PC of the raw flour would be explained by the fact that the not swollen starch granules remained dense reflecting the maximum of light entering the medium (Tetchi *et al.*, 2007). Consequently, pastes were turbid or opaque as described in the literature (Craig *et al.*, 1989).

Pastes obtained after boiling and baking are more transparent than native starch suspension in the raw flour (Tetchi *et al.*, 2007). The increasing of starch PC could be do to light refraction reduction by the granules remnant (Tetchi *et al.*, 2007).

According to Gossette *et al.* (1984) gelation is an aggregation of denatured molecule. The least gelation concentration of raw flour (2%) was lower from that of boiled (14%) and baked bulbils flour (8%) after 30 min. This result (Table 1) showed that boiling and baking increased the least gelation concentration in bulbils flours. But the least gelation from boiled bulbils flours was more increased than that of baked bulbils flours. The ability of protein to form gels and provide structural matrix for holding water flavors, sugars and food ingredients is useful in food application in new product development (Aremu *et al.*, 2006). Boiling and baking may have denatured the bulbils proteins and thus, caused more aggregation than in the raw bulbils flour. Udensiet *al.* (2001) indicated that gelation is a quality indicator influencing the texture of food such as soup. Flours with least gelation concentration are not suitable for infant formulation since they require more dilution and would result in reduced energy density in relation to volume (Ezeji and Ojmelukwe, 1993; Onwulezo and Nwabuyu, 2009).

The result of OAC is showed in Table 2. The OAC is an important property in food formulation because fats improve the flavour and mouth feel of foods (Kinsella, 1976). They are also important because of their storage stability and particulraty in the rancidity development (Siddiq *et al.*, 2010). The boiling water after 30min increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) the absorption capacity of olive oil, maize oil, red oil, dinor oil and sunflower oil from *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours. The OAC range between 39 ± 1.73 to $44 \pm 3.61\%$ for olive oil, 42 ± 5.57 to $55 \pm 2.65\%$ for maize oil, 48 ± 2.65 to $64 \pm 3\%$ for red oil, 50 ± 3 to $67 \pm 2.65\%$ dinor oil and 46 ± 2.65 to $60 \pm 6\%$ for sunflower oil. The OAC for these different oils were higer than those obtained for yam *D. dumetorum* flour (15%) (Medoua, 2005) and

lower in yam *D. rotundata* flours (137-228%) (Akubor and Badifu, 2004) and Ghanaian breadfruit (150-250%) (Appiah *et al.*, 2011b). The baking decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) the absorption capacity of olive oil, maize oil, red oil, dinor oil and sunflower oil from *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours. The OAC range between 34 ± 1.73 to $28 \pm 1.73\%$ for olive oil, 40 ± 2.65 to $30 \pm 2\%$ for maize oil, 45 ± 3.61 to $37 \pm 1.73\%$ for red oil, 47 ± 3 to $35 \pm 2.65\%$ dinor oil and 44 ± 2 to $38 \pm 2\%$ for sunflower oil. The OAC increasing could be attributed to the proteins denaturation and dissociation. This may be occurring boiling water which unmasks the non-polar residues from protein molecular (Narayana and Nearing, 1982). The OAC decreasing could be attributed to a decreasing in protein in *D. bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours which tend to reduce the hydrophobicity, and thereby causing a low fat binding to protein.

The presence of good degree of OAC in *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv "*Dugu-won*" bulbils flours may be suggested the presence of good lipophilic components which could be adapted to the production of sausages, soups and cakes. A high oil absorption capacity is valuable in ground meat formulations, meat replacers and extenders, doughnuts, pancakes and soups (Onimawo *et al.*, 2003).

Foams are used to improve texture, consistency and appearance of foods (Akubor, 2007). Results showed that foam capacity (FC) of *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours varied from $26.67 \pm 0.26\%$ in raw to $13 \pm 1.73\%$ for bulbils boiled during 30min and to $21.16 \pm 1.04\%$ for bulbils baked during the same time. The FC values obtained were higher than those reported by Amon *et al.* (2011) in flour from taro (*Colocasia esculenta*) cv *Yatan*.

Table 2. Oil absorption capacity for Olive oil, sunflower oil, maize oil, Dinor oil and red oil of aerial yam flours (*D. bulbifera*).

	Oil absorption (%)				
	Olive oil	Sunflower oil	Maize oil	Dinor oil	Red oil
Aerial yam flours and boiling times					
FNT0	35 ± 2^{DE}	46 ± 2.65^{DEF}	42 ± 5.57^{CDE}	50 ± 3^{CD}	48 ± 2.65^{EF}
FE10	34 ± 1.73^{DE}	44 ± 2^{CDE}	40 ± 2.65^{BCD}	47 ± 3^C	52 ± 3^{FGH}
FE20	30 ± 1.73^{BCD}	41 ± 2.65^{BCD}	37 ± 3.61^{BC}	40 ± 2.65^B	56 ± 2.65^H
FE30	28 ± 1.73^{ABC}	38 ± 2^{BC}	30 ± 2^A	35 ± 2.65^B	64 ± 3^{IJ}
Aerial yam flours and baking times					
FNT0	35 ± 2^{DE}	46 ± 2.65^{DEF}	42 ± 5.57^{CDE}	50 ± 3^{CD}	48 ± 2.65^{EF}
FF10	34 ± 1.73^{DE}	44 ± 2^{CDE}	40 ± 2.65^{BCD}	47 ± 3^C	45 ± 3.61^{DE}
FF20	30 ± 1.73^{BCD}	41 ± 2.65^{BCD}	37 ± 3.61^{BC}	40 ± 2.65^B	40 ± 1.73^{BC}
FF30	28 ± 1.73^{ABC}	38 ± 2^{BC}	30 ± 2^A	35 ± 2.65^B	37 ± 1.73^{AB}

The foaming stability of boiled and baked bulbils flours are presented in Fig. 1 and 2. The foam stability (FS) of *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) with boiling and baking time. The foam obtained from boiled bulbils flours stabilized faster (6h) than that obtained from baked bulbils flours (7h) after 30min. The reducing of foaming properties was related to protein denaturation.

These results agreed with the finding of Lin *et al.* (1974) that the native protein gives higher foam stability than denatured one. It's well know that, for a protein to have good foaming properties,

it has to be very soluble, because foam capacity requires rapid adsorption of protein at the air/water interface during whipping penetration into the surface layer and re-organisation at the interface (Amon *et al.*, 2011). There was an inverse relationships between foams capacity and foam stability. Flours with high foaming ability could form large air bubbles surrounded by thinner less flexible protein film.

This air bubble might be easier to collapse and consequently lowered the foaming stability (Jitngarmkusol *et al.*, 2008). This results suggest that bulbil of *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won*

flours may be useful in food system to improve textural and leavening characteristics such as ice-cream, cakes or topping and confectioning products where foaming property is important similar to that reported by Lee *et al* (1993).

Fig. 1. Foam stability of raw and boiled *Dioscorea bulbifera cv Dugu-won* bulbils flours at different temperature.

Fig. 2. Foam stability of raw and baked *Dioscorea bulbifera cv Dugu-won* bulbils flours at different temperature.

Swelling power of starch granules is an indication of the extent of associate forces within the granule (Moorthy and Ramanujan, 1986). The swelling power of starch granules is showed in Fig. 3 and 4. The result showed that boiling and baking increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) the value of swelling power after 30min.

Their value ranged respectively between 2.6 ± 0.01 to 14 ± 0.03 gH₂O/g DM and 2.6 ± 0.26 to 11.70 ± 0.42 g H₂O/g DM. The results agreed with the finding of Oulaï *et al.* (2014) which indicated in their study that cooked pulp of breadfruit after 20 min between 50°C

to 90°C increased the swelling power of pulp of breadfruit (1.4 to 17.09 gH₂O/g DM).

High swelling power is reported to constitute better thickening as well as a bulking agent (Iwoha and Nwankanma, 1998).

The flour solubility is water ability indicative to enter into starch granule. The solubility of raw flour from bulbils ranged between 10.20 ± 0.06 to $13.60 \pm 1.73\%$. When bulbils were boiled or baked after 30 min their solubility of flour ranged respectively from 14.12 ± 0.06 to $18.25 \pm 1.73\%$ and 12.15 to $15.20 \pm 1.22\%$ (Fig. 5 and 6). The result showed that boiling and baking after 30 min increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) the solubility of flour from bulbils.

This high solubility of boiling ($18.28 \pm 1.73\%$) and baking ($15.20 \pm 1.21\%$) bulbils flour, suggests that it is digestible and could be suitable for infant food formulation.

Fig. 3. Swelling power of raw and boiled *Dioscorea bulbifera cv Dugu-won* bulbils flours at different temperature.

Fig. 4. Swelling power of raw and baked *Dioscorea bulbifera cv Dugu-won* bulbils flours at different temperature.

Fig. 5. Solubility of raw and boiled *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours at different temperature.

Fig. 6. Solubility of raw and baked *Dioscorea bulbifera* cv *Dugu-won* bulbils flours at different temperature.

Conclusion

The results of this study indicated that boiling and baking times affected significantly ($P < 0.05$) the functional properties of aerial yam (*D. bulbifera*) flours cv *Dugu-won*. Aerial yam (*D. bulbifera*) flours from Côte d'Ivoire have a lot of potential in the food system. The high WAC of aerial yam flours was good providing agent and can thus be used as a thickener or gelling agent in various food products. The low bulk densities were as well as the high solubility. So, aerial yam flours would be useful in infant meals formulation.. However boiling ameliorated better functional properties of aerial yam (*D. bulbifera*) flours cv *Dugu-won* than baking. They may find an application in sausage production where there is enough needing oil.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by Ph.D. grant to the first author. The authors are grateful to Laboratory of Biocatalysis and Bioprocessing at the University Nangui Abrogoua (Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire) for technical assistance.

References

- Abara AE, Udosen EO, Eka OU.** 2000. Estimation of calcium, zinc, hydrocyanate, oxalate and phytate in *Dioscorea bulbifera* tuber. Global pure Applied Science, **6**, 449-453.
- Achy YJ, Koffi BKP, Ekissi ESG, Konan KH, Kouame PL.** 2016. Assessment of physico-chemical properties and anti-nutritional factors of flour from yam (*Dioscorea bulbifera*) bulbils in southeast Côte d'Ivoire. International journal of advanced research **4(12)**, 871-887.
- Adebooye OC, Singh V.** 2008. Physico-chemical properties of the flours and starches of two cowpea varieties (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp). Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies **9**, 92-100.
- Agunbiade SO, Sanni MO.** 2003. The effect of ambient temperature of cassava tubers on Starch quality. Pp 180-194. In: Root Crops. The small processor and development of Local Food Industries for market economy. Proceedings of the Eight Triennials Symposium of the International Society for Tropical Root Crops. African Branch (ISTRAC-AB) 12-14 Nov. IITA, Ibadan Nigeria. Page 993.
- Akissoe N, Joseph H, Christian M, Nago N.** 2003. Effect of tuber storage and pre and post blanching treatments on the physicochemical and pasting properties of dry yam flour. Food Chemistry **85**, 1414-1419.
- Akubor PI, Badifu GIO.** 2004. Chemical composition, functional properties and baking potential of African breadfruit kernel and wheat flour blends. International Journal of Food Science and Technology **39**, 223-229.

- Akubor PI.** 2007. Chemical, functional and cookie baking properties of soybean/maize flour blends. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* **44**, 619-622.
- Amon AS, Soro YR, Koffi BKP, Dué AE, Kouamé PL.** 2011. Biochemical characteristics of flours from Ivorian taro (*Colocasia esculenta*, cv *Yatan*) corn as affected by boiling time. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* **3(6)**, 424-435.
- Anderson RA, Conway HF, Pfeifer VF, Griffin EL.** 1969. Roll and extrusion-cooking of grain sorghum grits. *Cereal Science Today* **14**, 372-380.
- Appiah F, Oduro I, Ellis WO.** 2011. Proximate and mineral composition of *Artocarpus altilis* pulp flour as affected by fermentation. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition* **10**, 653-657.
- Aremu MO, Olonisakin A, Atolaye BO, Ogbu CF.** 2006. Some nutritional and functional studies of *Prosopis Africana*. *Electronic Journal of Environmental, Agricultural and Food Chemistry* **5**, 1640-1648.
- Aryee F, Oduro I, Ellis W, Afuakwa J.** 2006. The physicochemical properties of flour samples from the roots of 31 varieties of cassava. *Food Control* **17**, 916-922.
- Bourret-Cortadellas D.** 1973. Ethnobotanic study of the *Dioscorea*. Yam new Caledonia 3^{eme} cycle. *Familly of Science, Paris, France* P. 135.
- Brunnschweiler J, Mang D, Farah Z, Escher F, Conte-Petit B.** 2006. Structure-texture relationships of fresh pastes prepared from different yam (*Dioscorea* spp) varieties. *LWT-Food Science and Technology* **39**, 762-769.
- Chen MJ, Lin CW.** 2002. Factors affecting the water holding capacity of fibrinogen/plasma protein gels optimized by response surface methodology. *Journal of Food Science* **67**, 2579-2582.
- Chukwu O, Orhevbba BA, Mahmood BA.** 2010. Influence of Hydrothermal Treatments on Proximate Compositions of Fermented Locust Bean (Dawadawa). *Journal of Food Technology* **8(3)**, 99-101.
- Coffman CW, Garcia VC.** 1977. Functional properties and amino acid of a protein isolate from mung bean starch. *Journal of Food technology* **12**, 473-484.
- Coursey DG.** 1967. Yams. An account of the nature, cultivation and utilization of major root crops with special emphasis on humain, animal, industrial uses in tropical root crops. IDRC 22. Ottawa pp.25-35.
- Coursey DG.** 1973. Cassava as food: Toxicity and Technology. In Nestel, B and R Macintyre. (Eds) *Chronic Cassava Toxicity* Ottawa, Canada, IDRC-10^e pp. 27-36.
- Craig SA, Maningat CC, Seib PA, Hossney RC.** 1989. Starch paste clarity. *Cereal Chemistry* **66(3)**, 173-182.
- Degras L.** 1986. Yam, agricultural technologic and tropical products. *Maisonneuve and Cambridge; Agency for Cultural and Technical* pp. 409.
- Dengate HN.** 1984. Swelling, pasting and gellin of wheat starch, in *Advances in Cereal and Technology*, Ed. By Pomeranz Y. AACC Eagan Press, St Paul, MN, Chapitre **2**, pp 49-84.
- Diosady LL, Patton D, Rosen N, Rubin LJ.** 1985. Degradation of wheat starch in a single screw extruder: Mechano-kinetic breakdown of cooked starch. *Journal of Food Science* **50**, 1697-170.
- Eke OS, Akobundu ENT.** 1993. Functional properties of African yam bean (*Sphenostylis stenocarpa*) seed flour as affected by processing. *Chemistry* **48**, 337-340.
- Eke-Ejiofor J, Barber LI, Kiin-Kabari DB.** 2011. Effect of Pre-Boiling on the Chemical, functional and Pasting Properties of Rice. *Journal of Agriculture and Biology Science* **2**, 214- 219.
- Ezeji C, Ojmelukwe PC.** 1993. Effect of fermentation on the nutritional quality and functional properties of infant food formulations prepared from bambara-groundnut, fluted pumpkin and millet seeds. *Plant Food for human Nutrition* **44**, 267-276.

- Fagbemi TN, Oshoudi AA, Ipinmoroti KO.** 2006. Effects of processing in the functional properties of full fat and defatted fluted pumpkin seed flours. *Journal of Food and Technology* **4**, 70-79.
- FAO.** 1985. Production year book. Food and Agriculture Organisation of United Nations Rome **1985**, P. 39.
- FAO.** 1999. Food and agriculture organization of the United Nations Production Yearbook Vol 53. FAO statistics 1999. FAO, Rome Italy.
- Gossett PW, Rizvi SSH, BakerRC.** 1984. Quantitative analysis of gelation in egg protein systems *Food Technology* **38(5)**, 67-96.
- Hsu CL, Chen W, Weng Y-M, Tseng C-Y.** 2003. Chemical composition, physical properties, and antioxidant activities of yam flours as affected by different drying methods. *Food Chemistry* **83**, 85-92.
- Jimoh KO, Olatidoye OP.** 2009. Evaluation of physicochemical and rheological characteristics of soybean fortified yam flour. *Journal of Applied Biosciences* **13**, 703 -706.
- Jitngarmkusol S, Hongsuwankul J, Tananuawong K.** 2008. Chemical composition, functional properties and microstructure of defatted macademice flours. *Food Chemistry* **110**, 23-30.
- Kawabata A, Sawayama S, Nagashima N, Del Rosario RR, Nakamura M.** 1984. Some physicochemical properties of starches from cassava, arrow root and sago. *Journal of Japon Society Starch Sciences* **31**, 224-232.
- Kinsella JE.** 1976. Functional properties of proteins in foods: a survey. *Cr Revied of Food Science and Nutrition* **7**, 219-280.
- Kinsella JE.** 1979. Functional properties of soy proteins. *Journal of the American Oil Chemists Society* **56(3)**, 242-258.
- Kohnhorst AL, Uebersax MA, Zabik ME.** 1990. Production and functional characteristics of protein concentrates. *Journal of American Oil Chemistry Society* **67**, 285-292.
- Koné D, Koné MF, Djè KM, Dabonné S, Kouamé PL.** 2014. Effect of cooking time on biochemical and fonctional properties of flours from yam "kponan" (*Dioscorea cayenensis-rotundata*) *British Journal of Applied Science and Technology* **4(23)**, 3402-3418.
- Kulkarni KD, Kulkarni DN, Ingle UM.** 1991. Sorghum malt-based weaning formulations. Preparation, functional properties, and nutritive value. *Food and Nutrition Bulletin* **13**, 322-327.
- Lee CC, Love JA, Jonson LA.** 1993. Sensory and physical properties of cakes with bovine plasma products substituted for egg. *Cereal Chemistry* **7**, 18-23.
- Lewis NJ.** 1990. Physical properties of processing systems. Hartnolls Ltd Bodman, Cornwall, Great Britain.
- Libra MA, Gonnety JT, Ahi AP, Dabonné S, Ahipo ED, Kouamé LP.** 2011. Physicochemical changes in bulbils of two cultivars of *Dioscorea bulbifera* during the ripening period. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* **3(5)**, 327-331.
- Lin MJY, Humbert ES, Sosulki FW.** 1974. Certain functional properties of sunflower meal product. *Journal of food Science* **39**, 368-370.
- Masrizal MA, Giraud DW, Driskell JA.** 1997. Retention of vitamin C, iron, and beta-carotene in vegetables prepared using different cooking methods. *Journal of Food Quality* **20**, 403-418.
- Médoua NG.** 2005. Etude du durcissement post-récolte et des conditions de transformation des tubercules durcis en farine. Potentiel nutritionnel et technologique des tubercules durcis de l'igname *Dioscorea dumetorum* (kunth) pax Doctorat de Thèse/PhD. 254 p.

- Moorthy SN, Ramanujam T.** 1986. Variation in properties of starch in cassava varieties in relation to age of the crop. *Starch/Starke* **38**, 58-61.
- Narayana K, Nearing RMS.** 1982. Functional properties of raw and heat processed winged bean (*Psophocarpus tetragonolobus*) flour. *Journal of Food Science* **47**, 1534-1538.
- Nwabueze TU, Iwe MO, Akobundu ENT.** 2008. Physical characteristics and acceptability of extruded African bread fruit-based snack. *Journal of Food Quality* **31(2)**, 142-155.
- Oladele AK, Aina JO.** 2007. Chemical composition and functional properties of flour produced from two varieties of tiger nut (*Cyperus esculentus*). *African Journal of Biotechnology* **6**, 2473-2476.
- Onimawo AI, Egbekun KM.** 1998. *Comprehensive Food Science and Nutrition*. Revised edn Grace foundation pub. Jos.
- Onimawo IA, Nmerole EC, Idoko PI, Akubor PI.** 2003. Effects of fermentation on nutrient content and some functional properties of pumpkin seed (*Telfaria occidentalis*). *Plant Foods for Human Nutrition* **58(3)**, 1-9.
- Onwulenzon JC, Nwabugu CC.** 2009. Fermentation of millet (*Pennisetum americanum*) and Pigeon Pea (*Cajanus cajan*) seeds for flour production: Effects on composition and selected functional properties. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition* **8(6)**, 737-744.
- Oti E, Akobundu ENT.** 2007. Physical, Functional and amylograph pasting properties of cocoyam-soybean-crayfish flour blends. *Nigerian Food Journal* **25**, 161-170.
- Oulai SF, Ahi AP, Kouassi-Koffi JD, Gonnety JT, Faulet BM, Djè KM, Kouamé PL.** 2014. Treatments effects on functional properties of breadfruit (*Artocarpus altilis*) pulp flour haversted in Côte d'Ivoire. *International Journal of Recent Biotechnology* **2(4)**, 1-12.
- Padmashree TS, Vijayalakshim L, Puttaraj S.** 1987. Effect of traditional processing on functional properties of cowpea (*Vigna catjang*) flour. *Journal of Food Sciences and Technology* **24**, 221-225.
- Phillips RD, Chinnan MS, Branch AL, Miller J, Mcwatters KH.** 1988. Effects of pretreatment on functional and nutritional properties of cowpea meal. *Journal of Food Science* **53**, 805-809.
- Raja KCM.** 1992. Studies on alkali-modified cassava starch: Changes of structural and enzyme (Alphaamylase) susceptibility properties. *Starch/Starke* **44**, 133-136.
- Siddiq M, Ravi R, Harte JB, Dolan KD.** 2010. Physical and functional characteristics of selected dry bean (*Phaseolus vulgaricus* (L.) flours. *LWT-Journal of Food Sciences and Technology* **43**, 232-237.
- Survey,** 2012. Background Information on Bulbifera in Ghana.
- Tandall HD.** 1983. *Vegetables in the Tropics*. 1st Ed. Macmillan. Education Ltd. Houndmills Hampshire.
- Tetchi FA, Amani NG, Kamenan A.** 2007. Contribution to light transmittance modelling in starch media. *African Journal of Biotechnology* **6**, 569-575.
- Udensi A, Eke O.** 2000. Proximate composition and functional properties of flour produced from *Mucuna cochinchinensis* and *Mucuna utles*. In *Proceedings of the 1st Annual Conference of the College of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine Abia State University*. 10-13th Sept. 2000. Pp 170-174.
- Udensi EA, Eke O, Ukachukwu SN.** 2001. Effect of traditional processing on the the physicochemical properties of *Mucuna cochinchinensis* and *Mucuna utilis* flours. *Journal of Agriculture, Food Technology and Environment* **1**, 133-137.